

APPENDIX C

Activity explanation

Figure C.1 shows the interface that is presented to the students, in both the Human-Human version and the Human-Agent version. In the particular case of this example, the development of level 1 of 4 is presented. Students should look for the constellation showed to them, indicated as (4) in Figure C.1, among the set of stars (left half of the image C.1). The student must agree with his/her teammates about the solution they will select. In this case, one of the possible solutions are those indicated by the stars 1, 2 and 3, showed as (1) in Figure C.1. (Other solutions are stars 26, 27 and 28, (2) in Figure C.1, and 29, 30 and 31, (3) in Figure C.1). Because there are multiple solutions, three in this case, there is a high interdependence between peers. Also, the student who is taking part in the image (Figure C.1), has the role of selecting the blue star of the solution, (5) in Figure C.1, and must communicate to his/her teammates which blue star he/she will select. In (6) in Figure C.1, the messages sent by the three participants of the group are showed, while in (7) in Figure C.1, a message is displayed by the system. In (8) in Figure C.1, the messages that the student could send in this turn are displayed. Finally, in (9) in Figure C.1 is the button to send the selected message to his/her teammates.

Figure C.1 User interface